

TRANSLATE WORDS THAT HAVE NO ALTERNATIVE

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Toshpòlatova Dilafruz

a student of Faculty of English philology and translation studies at the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Nodirova ògiloy,

a student of Faculty of Foreign Language and Literature at the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Normurodova Durdona Asqar qizi

Teacher of Department of English philology and translation studies Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: *This article introduces how to translate in the translation process when there is no alternative to the original language word in the target language, i.e. translation methods. Each method is explained and expressed with specific examples*

Keywords: *Translation, originality, translation methods, analogy, transliteration, calque, figurative translation, subheadings, alternatives, similar words, lexical unit*

MUQOBILI YÒQ SÒZLARNI TARJIMA QILISH

Anotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola tarjima jarayonida asliyat tilidagi sòzning tarjima tilida muqobil varianti bòlmagan vaziyatda qanday tarjima qilish kerakligi haqida, ya'ni tarjima usullari haqida tanishtiradi. Har bir usul òziga xos misollar bilan ochib beriladi va tushuntiriladi.*

Kalit sòzlar: *Tarjima, asliyat, tarjima usullari, analogiya, transliteratsiya, kalkalash, tasviriy tarjima, sarlavha osti izohlari, muqobillik, òxshash sòzlar, leksik birlik*

Over the centuries, trade, handicrafts, agriculture, communication and relations between peoples and nations have developed. As relations developed, society began to feel the need for linguists. The norms of relations between the peoples, the agreements of the unions, the treaties of the peoples, the mutual covenants were resolved through knowledgeable translators. The translators have contributed to the harmonious, just and

harmonious coexistence of peoples. Translators have made an equal contribution to the mutual knowledge and study of peoples. In particular, A. Móminova commented on this: "The person engaged in translation, that is, the translator, is a bridge between two languages, two nations. Through his ability to translate, he reflects the most delicate aspects of the people, the nation. The culture, way of life, traditions and worldview of a nation are, of course, reflected in its language. For this reason, the translator has a great responsibility. It is important to translate alternative words in the language being translated, because the reader sees the work with the same eyes as the translator sees it and draws conclusions.

Each language has its own words that are not translated into another language. Such words are called non-alternative words. Examples of such words are words specific to each language and nationality. For example, words and concepts encountered in Uzbek may not be in other languages or may differ in content, form, and size. But such words express the nationality and identity of the Uzbek people. That is why it is important to convey the meaning and content of such words to the reader. While the translator is recreating the work in his own language, the translator should aim to make the reader feel the same way the translator understands and is affected by the work.

The alternative arises from an attempt to fully reflect the situation in the original in translation. The translator must make effective use of the richness of his language to provide alternative concepts in translation and to allow the reader to fully understand the original meaning. The translator must be able to translate non-alternative words using the same linguistic resources, absorbing their original meaning. So there are five ways to translate words that have no alternative. These are :

1. Transliteration
2. Subheading comments and explanation
3. Translate with similar words
4. Calque
5. Descriptive translation

1. Transliteration. This method is a method of matching the letters of a word in the original language to other letters in the target language in the absence of a word that gives the meaning of the original word in the target language. The purpose of translating words that have no alternative in this way is to preserve the original meaning of the word and convey it to the reader. An example of this is place names. For example, the English word Washington does not have an Uzbek translation. Therefore, since there is no

letter [W] in Uzbek, it is represented by the letter [V] in Uzbek and is written as Vashington . It is also represented in the Невтон style when it comes to the translation of Newton into Russian from popular English names.

2. Subheading comments and explanation.. In many cases, subtitled annotations and explanations are used to convey to the reader the meaning or concept that the words translated in the transliteration method convey. The following words are examples of this:

“He ate two pieces of handalak (a small honey melon) and drank several pialas

(a drinking bowl (as used in Central Asia)) of tea” [3, 2017, 10]

“Faqat bir-ikki tilim handalak yediyu uch-to'rt piyola choy ichdi” [4, 2017, 10]

“The guests in Qutidor's house were well respected people, treated with first and

second courses of many kinds of foods and sweets like khalva (pastry of nuts, sugar

and oil) and nisholda (type of custard)” [5, 2017, 54]

“Qutidorning tashqarisig'a er mehmonlar, ichkarisiga xotin mehmonlar to'lg'anlar, ular quyuuq, suyuq oshlar, holva, nisholda bilan izzatlanardilar”

3.Translate with similar words.. This method is another way of translating words that have no alternative in the language being translated, by translating the meaning closer. This method can also be thought of as translating by word analogy. In this process, if a word in the original language is not an alternative in the target language, a word similar to or close to the meaning of the word is selected. In this case, a phrase can be used instead of a single word. For example, there is no English word for "Halim" in Uzbek, but you can choose a similar dish that is boiled for a long time with wheat. When the appropriate word is not found, it can be given in the form of Porridge with wheat and stewed meat. It can also be given as nutritious meat porridge. Which word to choose depends on the skill of the translator.

4.Calque.. This method is a method of replacing the original lexical unit with its component - morphemes or words with lexically appropriate words in the translated text. The essence of this method is to create a firm expression in a new word or translation text by copying it from the structure of the original lexical unit. For example, Massculture is translated into Uzbek as Ommaviy madaniyat. In addition, the semi-translation also belongs to the method of sailing: South Korea-Janubiy Koreya, Old John – Qari Jon. Flat fish

– yassi baliq; Back brancher- orqa qarorda òyiradiganlar. The level of knowledge of the translator plays an important role in the process of translating words that have no alternative using the method of shielding.

5.Descriptive translation.. In this method of translating non-equivalent words, a phrase, phrase, or whole sentence may be used in the translation instead of a single word. For example, the English word "Spacewalk" is translated into Uzbek as "Kosmosga chiqish", and the Uzbek word "Havaskor" is translated into English as "Amateur talent activities".

A translator who uses these methods will ensure that the information provided in the translation retains as much meaning as possible and improves the quality of the translation. Of course, the work of a translator and the skill of translation play a big role here. Only when a translator has something like a writer - events, broad insights into the human psyche and the ability to fantasize, his work acquires a convincing, understandable, high artistic expressiveness and impact.

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